

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-179-AD-H-2% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	88	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 179
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	276.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 276.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	12/13/2022 20:45:10 CST		
Date Processed:	3/9/2023 20:35:42 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	11.432	301770	28.26	11886
2	12.583	295545	27.68	10923
3	13.882	235062	22.01	7765
4	15.808	235386	22.04	7149

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-208-AD-H-2% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	88	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 208
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	276.0nm
Run Time:	20.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 276.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	1/6/2023 17:38:31 CST		
Date Processed:	3/9/2023 20:37:19 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.978	103807	2.46	4291
2	12.045	42956	1.02	1557
3	13.193	4080294	96.51	140483
4	15.339	591	0.01	-63